

Sapogenins from *Asparagus adscendens* and *Chlorophytum arundinaceum*[†]

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Chlorophytum arundinaceum and *Asparagus adscendens* (Liliaceae) are reported to be used as tonic and are the ingredient of Ayurvedic formulations. Both are commonly known as 'Safed Musli' and in our investigations the root extract of both these plants displayed a good order of adaptogenic activity (details will be published elsewhere). Recently we have identified several constituents from the roots¹. In this communication we report the identification of sapogenins and sugars.

Dried and powdered roots of *A. adscendens* (5.7 kg) were extracted with MeOH (14 × 7.5 dm³). The extract was concentrated to 500 ml and H₂O (500 ml) was added. It was then extracted successively with n-hexane (6 × 500 ml; 24.8 g) and n-BuOH (25 × 250 ml; 80.13 g). Part of the BuOH extract (1 g) was hydrolysed with methanolic HCl (5% ; 5 h). The usual work-up yielded sapogenins (0.26 g) and sugars. Sugars were identified as xylose, arabinose and glucose by tlc in CHCl₃-MeOH-Me₂CO-H₂O (3 : 3 : 3 : 1) and n-BuOH-AcOH-H₂O (4 : 1 : 5) and comparison with authentic sugars. Preparative tlc of sapogenins in CHCl₃ yielded sapogenins A and B.

Similarly, dried and powdered roots of *C. arundinaceum* (3.5 kg) were extracted with MeOH (11 × 3.5 dm³). The extract was concentrated to 500 ml and H₂O (500 ml) added. The aqueous MeOH extract was then extracted with n-hexane (5 × 500 ml; 35 g) and n-BuOH (10 × 250 ml; 40 g). The BuOH extract (1 g) was refluxed with methanolic HCl (5% ; 5 h) which afforded sugars and sapogenins. The identity of sugars was established as arabinose, xylose and glucose by comparison with authentic material (co-*tlc*). Sapogenins (0.24 g) were chromatographed over silica gel (11 g) to provide sapogenins C-F.

Sapogenin A (0.02 g), m.p. 155°, *M*⁺ 412, was identified as stigmasterol (co-*tlc*, MS and ¹H nmr).

Sapogenin B (0.01 g), m.p. 190–92° [*α*]_D –80° (CHCl₃), *M*⁺ 416, *v*_{max} 964, 925, 905, 880 (925 > 900 cm⁻¹, 2*S*-configuration), was identified as sarsasapogenin (co-*tlc*, MS). Sapogenin C (0.018 g), m.p. 155°, was identified as stigmasterol (co-*tlc*, MS). Sapogenin D (0.01 g), m.p. 200°, [*α*]_D –69° (CHCl₃), *M*⁺ 416, *v*_{max} 960, 920, 900, 860 (900 > 920 cm⁻¹, 2*S*(*R*)), was identified as tigogenin (co-*tlc*, MS). Sapogenin E (0.012 g), m.p. 240°, [*α*]_D –80° (CHCl₃), *v*_{max} 927 > 902 cm⁻¹ (2*S*(*s*)), *M*⁺ 432, was identified as neogitogenin² by comparison with literature data (m.p., [*α*]_D, MS). Sapogenin F (0.016 g), m.p. 266°, [*α*]_D –39° (C₆H₆N), *M*⁺ 448, was identified as tokorogenin by mass spectral fragmentation, ¹³C nmr spectrum and comparison with literature data³ (m.p., [*α*]_D).

These studies indicates that *A. adscendens* contains saponins of stigmasterol and sarsasapogenin, whereas saponins of stigmasterol, tigogenin, neogitogenin and tokorogenin are found in *C. arundinaceum*.

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References

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